

Research Article

Using Bayesian network analysis in social sciences: A case study of domestic water and energy use

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Abstract

Understanding the factors that shape household water and energy use is essential for designing targeted conservation interventions that promote both sustainability and well-being. While studies in this area often rely on traditional “frequentist” statistical methods, which can struggle to capture the complex interdependencies among demographic, behavioural, psychological, and material influences. This paper introduces Bayesian network (BN) analysis as a novel and adaptable method with useful applications in water and energy studies and a wide variety of other social sciences. The paper offers a primer on how to conduct BN analysis, including underlying logic and range of choice of software platforms, before presenting a brief worked example based on the authors’ current research into household water and energy consumption in a UK city. The paper shows how Bayesian networks can generate valuable insights from relatively small and complex datasets, capture non-linear relationships, and support scenario-based reasoning, making them well-suited for exploratory studies, “what if?” scenario-testing and policy effectiveness review. The findings contribute to a more nuanced understanding of domestic water and energy consumption and offer a practical framework that can inform the design of targeted, evidence-based interventions to encourage sustainable water and energy use in households. We argue that there is much to be gained by proliferation of this analytical approach throughout the social sciences.

Key words: Conditional probability, household behaviour, sustainability, survey data, water demand management

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1. Introduction

Understanding household water and energy consumption patterns is essential for developing targeted conservation strategies to meet climate targets (Inman and Jeffrey 2006; Russell and Fielding 2010; Staddon 2010; Simpson et al. 2019). In response to climate change mitigation targets and growing concerns over urban resilience, governments and utilities are increasingly interested in understanding not only how much water and energy is consumed, but also why and under what conditions. Cities such as Bristol, UK, provide useful case studies: sustainability goals align with the need for behavioural insights,

but limited understanding of household behaviour still hampers conservation efforts. Part of the problem is that accurately modelling household consumption behaviour is methodologically challenging. Traditional quantitative methods, such as regression analysis, often assume linear relationships and independence among variables, potentially oversimplifying the multifaceted nature of human behaviour (Gregory and Leo 2003). Moreover, such methods usually assume that analysts have already identified dependent and independent variables. Qualitative methods, on the other hand, offer depth but lack the ability to quantify and generalise findings across populations (Polit and Beck 2010).

Bayesian networks (BNs) are a powerful methodological alternative capable of addressing these limitations. As probabilistic graphical models, BNs enable the explicit modelling of complex interdependencies among variables, represented as a network diagram made up of nodes representing variables connected by arrows suggesting causality (Pearl 1988; Heckerman et al. 1995). The hypothesised networks can then be trained on data to generate conditional probability tables denoting the actual strengths of hypothesised relationships between nodes. Unlike traditional statistical models, BNs do not require assumptions of linearity or especially large datasets and can accommodate different variable types. They are also particularly well-suited for representing both direct and indirect relationships, incorporating uncertainty, and updating predictions as new data becomes available (Uusitalo 2007; Giordano et al. 2017). This makes them especially valuable in social survey research where datasets are often small, multidimensional, and complex due to incompleteness or heterogeneity of variable types.

Despite their established effectiveness in some social and environmental research contexts (Borsuk et al. 2004; Beaudequin et al. 2017; Giordano et al. 2017; Cronk and Bartram 2017; Ding 2020), the application of BNs specifically to household water and energy consumption research and in the social sciences in general remains limited (Phan et al. 2016; Beaudequin et al. 2017; Bessani et al. 2020; Kaikkonen et al. 2021a, 2025). This is possibly due to the tendency for social scientists to be trained in frequentist statistical analysis, with little exposure to alternative approaches including BN analysis. Addressing this methodological gap represents a significant opportunity for advancing both academic understanding of complex social phenomena and designing effective social policy. By leveraging BNs researchers can achieve a more comprehensive and nuanced analysis of the multiple factors shaping consumption patterns, enabling policymakers and practitioners to design more precisely targeted and context-sensitive conservation strategies.

This article explores the methodological strengths and practical utility of BN analysis within household water and energy research specifically and social sciences more generally. It demonstrates how BNs can effectively navigate complex data landscapes, elucidate hidden or indirect relationships among key variables, and facilitate scenario simulations to anticipate and optimize the effectiveness of potential interventions. We discuss use cases and software options before outlining our application of BNs to specific challenges in understanding domestic water and energy consumption in a UK city. We conclude with discussion of how barriers to uptake may be addressed.

2. The general use case for using Bayesian networks in social research

BNs offer a robust, flexible framework for analysing complex systems where multiple factors interact to influence outcomes. At the heart of this approach is Bayes' theorem, which describes how to update the probability of a hypothesis based on new evidence by combining prior belief with the likelihoods derived from observed data. Most crucially, BNs readily accommodate the idea that the extent to which a given variable affects an outcome may itself be contingent on the state of other variables in the network. Following from this feature, BNs do not require an assumption of independence between variables as do frequentist methods such as regression modelling. This makes BNs especially valuable in household consumption research, where behaviours are shaped by a dynamic interplay of demographic, psychological, material, and contextual influences.

Conceptually, a BN represents variables as nodes and the probabilistic (conditional) interdependencies between them as directed edges (arrows), forming a network diagram technically known as a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) (Fig. 1). Nodes with outgoing edges are 'parents', and those they connect to are 'children'. The diagram is 'acyclic' because no path loops back to its starting point. In this case, you can see that pre-existing environmental awareness on the part of the householder can directly affect the likelihood of water saving (the edge linking "environmental awareness" to "propensity to save water"). But as each edge or arrow also indicates the extent to which one variable depends on the state of another, we can model the extent to which the state of a parent node activates the child node. In this case, the probability that a household adopts

Figure 1. Simplified DAG depicting "propensity of save water" as a contingent outcome of "environmental awareness" and "available infrastructure".

water-saving behaviours may increase if residents are environmentally aware and efficient appliances are available, but without the environmental awareness presence of available infrastructure would not be expected to have the same effect on propensity to save water. This type of visual model captures both direct effects and interactions among conditions.

To make the logic concrete, Table 1 shows a simple conditional probability table (CPT) for the outcome “propensity to save water” given two parents, “environmental awareness” and “efficient appliances available”. The numbers are illustrative but reflect plausible patterns we observe.

Table 1. Example CPT showing the effect of awareness and appliances on water-saving behaviour.

Environmental awareness	Efficient appliances	P (save water = Yes)
High	Yes	0.78
High	No	0.42
Low	Yes	0.35
Low	No	0.15

Note: In the full model (see sections four and five), probabilities are learned from data and updated automatically as additional evidence is observed; here we use round numbers only to illustrate the mechanics.

As Table 1 illustrates, households with high awareness and efficient appliances are much more likely (0.78) to engage in water-saving behaviours (e.g., shorter showers, turning off taps while soaping). If awareness is high but appliances are inefficient, the probability falls to 0.42, highlighting how material constraints limit action. Even with low awareness, efficient appliances still help (0.15 to 0.35), though the effect is smaller.

These results also allow quick “what-if” style queries of the kind often used in policy discussions. For instance, moving from low awareness/inefficient appliances to high awareness/efficient appliances increases the probability of saving water by 0.63. An appliance-only upgrade yields a 0.20 gain, while an awareness-only campaign yields a 0.27 gain. Such scenario testing demonstrates how BNs quantify the combined psychological and material influences on behaviour and provide a transparent way to explore intervention options.

These conditional relationships are quantified in CPT, which show how likely an outcome is under different combinations of influencing factors. For example, the survey or observational data underlying a BN noted in Fig. 1 might indicate that households with high environmental awareness and access to water-efficient appliances have a 78% probability of engaging in shorter showers and turning off taps whilst brushing teeth or hand washing dishes. In contrast, when awareness is high, but appliances are inefficient (e.g. only bathtub available) and routines are fixed, the probability drops to 42%. This ability to combine psychological, material, and behavioural conditions—and instantly update probabilities when new data becomes available (called “revisiting the priors” in BN-speak)—makes BN a powerful tool for exploring “what-if” scenarios that traditional linear models cannot easily capture. The example in Fig. 1 is

deliberately simplified to illustrate this basic Bayesian logic and will be further developed later in this paper.

The strengths of BNs for this kind of research lie in several key capabilities:

- Handling missing or incomplete data: BNs estimate probabilities even when some data points are missing, reducing bias and enhancing the reliability of results in small or imperfect datasets, a common feature in household-level survey research.
- Accommodating mixed data types: they work with both categorical and continuous variables, whether derived from self-reports (e.g., attitudes) or observations (e.g., meter readings).
- Identifying direct and indirect relationships: unlike traditional regression techniques, BNs do not assume variable independence and can reveal indirect pathways. For example, a psychological factor such as environmental concern might influence water use indirectly by affecting daily routines or the adoption of efficient technologies.
- Testing “what-if” scenarios: researchers and decision-makers can simulate hypothetical interventions (e.g., increasing awareness through education) and estimate how likely these changes would impact behaviour, all while accounting for uncertainty.

BNs have already demonstrated their value in a range of environmental and resource management domains. For example, Borsuk et al. (2004) used a BN to predict and manage eutrophication risks in aquatic systems under uncertainty, supporting policy choices between alternative interventions, while BN applications in agriculture decision modelling and integrated catchment planning emerged in the late 2000s (Phan et al. 2016; Keshtkar et al. 2013). Beaudequin et al. (2017) applied BNs to water recycling schemes, integrating expert knowledge and limited monitoring data to evaluate microbial health risks and guide adaptive management. More broadly, BNs have been used to forecast floods by integrating climate predictions, infrastructure data, and urban risk mapping—for example, Zhang et al. (2025) modelled flood control dependency and cascading failures in the Pearl River Delta, while a 2025 study using hierarchical BN models improved forecasting of river stages across gauge networks. In ecological risk assessment, a BN analysing urban waterlogging in Wuhan (Li et al. 2023), demonstrated how BN modelling can identify critical hazard pathways under complex, multi-stressor conditions. Furthermore, Kaikkonen et al. (2021b) provide a systematic review of BN applications in environmental risk assessment, highlighting how these models can support transparent, evidence-based decision-making under uncertainty in complex, multi-stressor ecological systems.

These examples illustrate how BNs can combine diverse data sources, handle uncertainty, and support scenario-based reasoning to inform real-world social interventions. BNs offer powerful advantages for tackling complex social science challenges such as social inequality, sedentarism and criminal deviance. For example, Yan et al. (2024) used BNs to explore the confounding role of gender in the relationships among demographics, mental health, and violent crime behaviours. And Buck et al. (2019) created a BN using Eurobarometer survey data to identify key factors influencing sedentarism, which is a key precursor of obesity and obesity-related health outcomes. In both cases, the BNs were used to show how outcomes (violent criminality and sedentarism) are

shaped by contingently interrelated factors. A clear implication is that effective social policy cannot be based on simple cause-effect models but rather must address the nonlinear and probabilistic relationships between variables within complex social systems.

A key reason why BNs have not been used as much by social scientists to date is that they can be quite computationally demanding. Building a BN often involves learning the network structure from data (referred to as “training the model”), which is computationally intensive, especially when algorithms like hill climbing, constraint-based methods, or score-based search are applied. Moreover, performing probabilistic inference, which involves computing posterior distributions across the network, can also be computationally expensive. Advances in computing (e.g., cloud platforms, parallel processing) and software (e.g., bnlearn, pgmpy, BayesiaLab) have made BNs much more practical as we shall see in the next section.

3. Review of software options for Bayesian network analysis

Bayesian network analysis can be implemented using a range of software tools operating efficiently on readily available computing hardware. And whilst there are numerous commercially available platforms for performing BN analysis, there are also open source options, particularly via the coding platform R. Each available platform varies in terms of usability, flexibility, computational power, and cost, making it important for researchers to choose one that best fits their data and analytical needs (Mahjoub and Kalti 2011).

Those interested in exploring the technical capabilities and differences between commonly used BN software packages (such as Netica, GeNIe, Hugin, BayesiaLab, STATA, or R with the bnlearn package) should refer to the detailed overview provided in Suppl. material 1. In Table 2 we discuss in more detail the advantages and limitations of these software packages.

Table 2. Advantages and limitations of available of most used software for Bayesian network analysis.

Software/Library*	Advantages	Limitations	Website
Netica	Intuitive graphical interface, widely adopted	Limited scripting, license required	norsys.com
GeNIe	User-friendly, free for academic use	Limited scalability, basic analytics	bayesfusion.com
Hugin	Advanced inference tools; supports hybrid models	Expensive, steep learning curve	hugin.com
BayesiaLab*	Sophisticated visualisation and analytics	High cost; complex interface	bayesia.com
STATA	Well-known platform; robust statistical tools	Limited BN functionality; costly	stata.com
R (bnlearn)	Free; flexible scripting; integrates with other tools	Requires programming skills	bnlearn.com

Although using R with the bnlearn package (R Core Team 2025) required a substantial learning investment, it was employed in the study presented in sections four and five. This choice was guided by several factors aligned with the exploratory and methodological aims of the research:

- It is open-source and freely available, promoting accessibility, transparency, and reproducibility.
- It offers extensive flexibility for both structure learning (via score-based and constraint-based algorithms) and parameter estimation.
- It integrates seamlessly with other R packages, such as gRain for inference, FactoMineR for dimensionality reduction, and ggplot2 for data visualisation, enabling a cohesive analytical workflow.
- Its script-based environment allows for custom modelling approaches that accommodate the study's specific challenges, including a small sample size, high-dimensional data, mixed variable types, and partial missingness.

By supporting tailored workflows and facilitating transparent model development, the R environment with bnlearn proved to be the most suitable platform. It enabled precise control over each stage of the analysis, from data preprocessing to model construction and interpretation, making it ideal for research focused on methodological innovation in household water and energy studies.

4. Applying Bayesian networks to better understand domestic water and energy use

Our research has applied BN analysis to explore the complex factors influencing household water and energy consumption behaviours in the UK (La Matta Romero et al. 2024; unpublished manuscript, La Matta Romero et al.). The underlying dataset, derived from a questionnaire survey conducted in Bristol, England, offers a multidimensional view of domestic life, encompassing sociodemographic characteristics, housing features, psychological factors, and behavioural habits. Given the small sample size ($N = 24$) and the high number of variables (over 100), a BN approach was selected for its capacity to model conditional dependencies, handle incomplete data, and infer probabilistic relationships in a transparent and flexible manner.

A key challenge in household survey research of this type is data sparsity. As in our case, data is sparse because of the time cost of collecting surveys over multiple study phases and because not all respondents completed all questions (e.g. due to sickness or other unavailability). Moreover, although the number of unique households surveyed was small, the number of variables assessed was large (over 100) and not necessarily independent of one another. Traditional statistical methods may struggle under such conditions, but BNs are well-suited to manage incomplete datasets through probabilistic inference. Missing values are treated not as nulls but as unknowns, allowing the model to estimate conditional probabilities based on the available information, thereby minimising potential bias.

Given the high dimensionality of the survey data, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied within thematically grouped clusters of variables to reduce complexity. "Dimensionality" refers to the number of attributes, columns, or variables in a dataset. For survey data, each question or demographic variable (e.g., age, income, education, attitudes, behaviours) adds a dimension. These clusters included: sociodemographic factors, household characteristics, awareness, motivation, consciousness, behaviours, and routines. PCA allowed for the condensation of each group into a smaller set of "principal components"

that retained the most useful information. For example, had we collected survey data about “handedness” amongst respondents, this information would have been down weighted or otherwise factored out in the resulting priority list of explanatory factors. Prioritised factors were then used as input variables in the BN model, preserving interpretability while improving computational efficiency and avoiding model overfitting. Overfitting occurs when a statical or machine learning model tries to “learn” noise created by multicollinearity or error. This can lead to a model that looks great but performs poorly on new unseen data.

To ensure analytical consistency, after application of PCA, mixed data types were harmonised through preprocessing: continuous, ordinal and categorical responses were transformed into binary variables or categorical variables with the fewest possible categorical intervals. Each identified factor (e.g., sociodemographic factors, household characteristics) was represented as a node in the BN. As noted above, the connections (edges) between nodes represent conditional dependencies, describing how one variable is hypothesised (based on prior belief or knowledge about the network) to influence another. To train the network, structure learning algorithms were employed to uncover relationships directly from a subset of the collected data. In our research, the Hill-Climbing (HC) algorithm was used to iteratively adjust the BN by adding, removing, or reversing connections to improve model fit, while Tabu Search was used in par-

Figure 2. Steps followed in the Bayesian network modelling process.

allel to avoid the algorithm becoming trapped in local optima by allowing exploration of alternative network configurations. Hill climbing and Tabu Search are common algorithms used in constructing BNs – many other alternatives are discussed in detail by Scutari (2010) and Scutari and Denis (2022). Once a network structure was identified, conditional probability tables (CPTs) were estimated for each node using the available survey data. CPTs describe how the probability of each outcome (e.g., adopting water-saving routines) changes in response to different combinations of parent factors (e.g., environmental awareness, household infrastructure).

Model performance was assessed using fit metrics such as log-likelihood, the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), and the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). These measures helped balance complexity and explanatory power, ensuring the resulting model remained both statistically robust and interpretable, while avoiding overfitting given the small dataset. The main stages of this analytical process are summarised in Figure 2, which presents the sequential steps from data collection to interpreting findings.

Finally, external validation was undertaken to increase confidence in the plausibility and interpretability of the Bayesian network. This process combined expert discussions and literature-based checks. Preliminary network structures and identified dependencies were reviewed in depth with academic colleagues and researchers experienced in BN modelling, social practice theory, and household water and energy consumption behaviours. These exchanges were used to critically assess whether the connections identified by the model aligned with established behavioural theories and made conceptual sense in light of existing domain expertise.

In addition, the dependencies highlighted by the BN were cross-checked against findings reported in the wider literature on domestic water and energy use. This helped ensure that the relationships emerging from the analysis were consistent with established knowledge and did not conflict with well-supported empirical evidence. Where the BN revealed connections that were not clearly supported by prior studies, these were revisited and interpreted with caution, acknowledging their exploratory nature.

Although this validation did not involve direct input from household stakeholders' workshops, combining researcher expertise with evidence from existing literature provided an additional layer of scrutiny to the model. This process improved confidence in the structure and interpretation of the BN, strengthening its reliability as an exploratory analytical tool for understanding the drivers of household water and energy consumption.

With the BN model validated, the next step involved using probabilistic inference to explore interdependencies and simulate scenarios. For instance, the model could assess how a change in one factor—such as increased awareness or a shift in household composition—might influence other variables, such as the probability of adopting water-saving practices. This kind of analysis allows researchers to go beyond simple correlation and test plausible “what-if” questions about behavioural dynamics, policy interventions, or future trends. This is exactly what we illustrate in the following section, where we present example scenarios generated from the BN model to demonstrate its practical application (Fig. 3).

5. Results and key findings

In our study, over 100 individual survey items were grouped into 11 thematic clusters based on conceptual similarity and data structure (Fig. 3). These clusters were later reviewed again before testing the first BN model.

Fig. 3 presents a DAG showing hypothetical dependencies between these clusters in a much more sophisticated (and therefore realistic) way than in Fig. 1. The arrows between clusters (identified through PCA) represent potential conditional relationships, as identified through the BN structure learning process described in the previous section.

Figure 3. Conceptual network showing dependencies between the different variables. Legend: sociodemographic factors (SD), household characteristics (HC), awareness (A), consciousness (C), devices and appliances (D), recycling habits (R), practices (P), outdoor habits (O), comfort (CM), transportation and travel habits (T), and behaviour (B). Significant arcs are darker tones of black (usually >0.8–1.0 in probability strength) or lighter black (between 0.5–0.8). Light grey arcs are observing a weak relationship (usually 0.1–0.5) and should be considered as less reliable in strength with potential to change.

The most important difference between Fig. 1 and Fig. 3 is that the model represented in Fig. 3 was actually trained on a subset of the collected data, with the results that contingent probability tables were generated and the relative significance of hypothesized relationships was assessed—represented as relatively bold or light edges.

5.1. Key patterns and dependencies

The Bayesian Network revealed several important patterns of dependence:

- Environmental awareness (A) emerged as a central predictor of self-reported behaviours (B), influencing not only direct actions (P) (e.g., turning off taps, reducing heating use) but also indirectly shaping practices through device adoption (D) and consciousness (C).
- Household characteristics (HC), such as property type, number of occupants, and presence of utility meters, were linked to both awareness (A) and comfort-related preferences (CM), suggesting material conditions shape the context in which conservation behaviours occur.
- Daily routines, such as dishwashing frequency or shower length (captured in cluster P), were strongly connected to both psychological factors (e.g., motivation, awareness) (A, C) and infrastructure-related elements (D) (e.g., availability of efficient appliances), illustrating the intertwined nature of habits and materiality.

These dependencies reflect not only direct influences but also indirect pathways, sequences of arcs that show how one variable exerts influence through intermediary nodes. For example, awareness may increase the likelihood of using water-efficient appliances, which in turn reduces total water consumption. Standard regression approaches would struggle to detect such pathways. Importantly, while BNs uncover statistical dependencies, they do not inherently prove causality in the way controlled experiments can. As described by Pearl (1988), the relationships captured in a BN should be interpreted as probabilistic associations, which may suggest causal directions but cannot confirm them without additional longitudinal or experimental evidence. However, this does not undermine the value of BN analysis. On the contrary, BNs are particularly powerful for hypothesis generation, identifying plausible causal pathways, and supporting decision-making under uncertainty, especially in complex social-ecological systems where controlled experiments are often not feasible. By mapping interdependencies and testing “what-if” scenarios, BNs provide a structured, evidence-informed foundation that can guide future research and the design of targeted interventions, even in the absence of definitive causal proof.

5.2. Key insights into household water and energy consumption uncovered through Bayesian network analysis

The application of Bayesian network analysis revealed that household water consumption is shaped by a complex interplay of psychological, behavioural, and material factors. Rather than being driven by any single determinant, water and energy use practices emerged from dynamic combinations of awareness, routines, infrastructure, and social context. Three particularly salient insights stand out from the analysis:

1. Psychological factors as indirect influencers:

Variables reflecting environmental concern, perceived responsibility, and awareness of personal impact were not always strongly linked to self-reported water conservation practices. Instead, these psychological factors exerted indirect influence through intermediate variables such as device adoption (e.g.,

installing efficient dishwashers or low-flow showerheads), conscious routines (e.g., timing showers, adjusting tap usage) and material investments or infrastructure (e.g., choosing water-saving appliances, improve insulation).

This finding suggests that psychological dispositions may operate by shaping decision-making contexts or preferences rather than triggering immediate behavioural change. For example, individuals who scored high in environmental awareness were more likely to engage in forward-planning behaviours (e.g., comparing appliance efficiency), which then translated into lower water usage through more efficient practices.

2. Daily practices and routines as key drivers:

Everyday routines, such as the frequency of dishwashing, showering, or toilet flushing, emerged as strong direct predictors of water consumption. These patterns were more closely linked to total usage than sociodemographic attributes such as age, gender, or income. For instance, households that reported fixed, repeated daily water-use habits exhibited more consistent consumption patterns regardless of demographic profile.

This reinforces the idea that water consumption is a product of embedded practices, not isolated decisions. Behavioural interventions that aim to disrupt or reshape habitual routines (e.g., through reminders, nudges, or material changes in the home) may be more effective than those focused solely on attitudes or knowledge dissemination.

3. Material conditions enable or constrain behaviour:

The BN also highlighted the role of material conditions, such as appliance efficiency, household infrastructure, and the presence or absence of water meters. These factors often mediated the relationship between psychological intentions and actual behaviours. For example, even among participants who expressed high conservation awareness, water usage remained high in homes lacking efficient appliances or metering systems.

This finding supports the notion that behaviour change cannot occur independently of material arrangements. Interventions must therefore address the material constraints and enablers of sustainable practices, such as upgrading infrastructure, incentivising efficient technologies, or ensuring equitable access to water-saving resources.

Together, these insights underscore the importance of integrated intervention strategies that account for psychological motivations, habitual routines, and material infrastructures. Bayesian network analysis was instrumental in identifying these layered dependencies, offering a nuanced understanding of how change might occur in practice. This methodological approach enables the design of more targeted, context-sensitive policies and programmes that reflect the realities of everyday water use in high-income urban settings like Bristol, UK.

These insights suggest several avenues for real-world policy application. For instance, utilities could use BN models as decision-support tools to identify household profiles most responsive to conservation efforts, even in the absence of full datasets. Scenario testing with the BN framework could inform targeted outreach, such as offering appliance subsidies to households where awareness is high, but material enablers (e.g., efficient technologies) are lacking. Moreover, policies aiming to reshape routines (e.g., promoting water-use dashboards or behavioural nudges) could be refined by testing their effects

within the model before large-scale implementation. In this way, the BN approach moves beyond diagnosis to support adaptive, evidence-informed conservation planning.

6. Limitations, challenges, and future directions of using Bayesian networks

While Bayesian networks offer significant strengths in modelling interdependent variables and managing uncertainty, their application in social research comes with several challenges. First, the small sample size (24 households) used in this study, although appropriate for exploratory work, limits the statistical power of structure and parameter learning. While probabilistic inference allows for analysis despite incomplete or sparse data, results should be interpreted cautiously and supplemented by expert knowledge, as was done in this study.

Another limitation involves the presence of missing data. For example, some water and energy meter readings were incomplete. Although BNs can estimate missing values through inference, this inevitably introduces additional uncertainty. Future research could address this by incorporating smart meter or real-time sensor data to enhance data granularity and completeness.

The process of structure learning also poses computational demands. Algorithms such as Hill-Climbing and Tabu Search are resource-intensive, particularly when applied to high-dimensional datasets. In this case, dimensionality reduction via PCA was necessary to improve model efficiency and interpretability. Further development of scalable algorithms or the use of parallel computing would enhance the feasibility of applying BNs in larger datasets.

Additionally, while BNs are excellent for identifying probabilistic dependencies, they do not establish causality unless supported by longitudinal data or experimental designs (Pearl 1988). The connections in a BN represent associations, not temporal sequences or causal mechanisms. As such, findings should be interpreted as suggestive rather than conclusive.

Discretising continuous variables can lead to information loss if cut-points are poorly defined. Careful and theoretically informed discretisation is essential to maintain analytical validity.

Finally, communicating BN results to non-specialist stakeholders can be challenging. Although network diagrams are visually intuitive, interpreting conditional probability tables and scenario outputs requires careful framing. This limits the direct transferability of results into policy unless supported by clear visualisations or participatory interpretation tools. Moreover, the open-source tools used (e.g., BNlearn in R) require technical proficiency, which may constrain their adoption outside of research environments. Wider use will benefit from improved interfaces, training, and interdisciplinary collaboration.

To manage these limitations, this study employed several mitigation strategies. Dimensionality reduction via PCA helped to reduce the computational burden and minimise the risk of overfitting. Expert-informed structure learning guided the development of the network, ensuring that dependencies were conceptually and empirically sound. Transparent and reproducible scripting in R further supported methodological rigour, while the use of textual visualisation

and narrative framing aimed to improve accessibility across interdisciplinary audiences.

Looking ahead, several avenues offer promise for advancing the use of Bayesian networks in household water and energy research. Scaling up future studies with larger and more diverse samples would improve the generalisability of findings and enable subgroup analyses. Integrating smart technologies, such as sensor data or real-time smart meter readings, could enhance temporal precision and reveal more granular behavioural patterns. Hybrid modelling approaches that combine BNs with agent-based or system dynamics models may yield deeper insights into system-level dynamics and feedback loops. Incorporating participatory modelling, where stakeholders co-construct networks or interpret scenario outcomes, could also enhance the practical relevance and uptake of findings. Finally, the potential of BN models as decision-support tools—capable of informing utility planning, policy testing, and targeted behaviour change interventions under uncertainty—merits further exploration.

By addressing both methodological constraints and practical application needs, future research can unlock the full potential of Bayesian networks as a tool for understanding and transforming household sustainability practices. Future work could compare BN with individual-level approaches such as multinomial probit models, which may highlight complementary strengths.

7. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the value of Bayesian network analysis as a powerful and flexible methodological tool for understanding household water and energy consumption in high-income contexts. By modelling interdependencies among psychological, behavioural, and material factors, BNs offer a more nuanced and dynamic view of consumption than traditional statistical or purely qualitative approaches.

A key strength of the BN approach lies in its ability to handle small, multidimensional datasets through PCA-driven dimensionality reduction and probabilistic inference, even when data are incomplete. The method also captures both direct and indirect pathways, revealing how environmental awareness and infrastructure interact with daily routines and appliance use to influence consumption patterns. Crucially, it supports scenario-based reasoning, enabling researchers and policymakers to explore “what-if” interventions—such as awareness campaigns or equipment upgrades—under realistic conditions and with quantified uncertainty.

Despite these strengths, the study also acknowledges several challenges. The small sample size, data gaps, and the computational intensity of structure learning all present limitations that must be addressed in future research. In particular, integrating richer datasets, such as smart meter or sensor data, and developing tools that enhance interpretability for non-specialist audiences will be essential for broader application.

Methodologically, this research advances a transparent and reproducible framework for using Bayesian networks in sustainability studies. It offers a clear process for structuring survey data, reducing dimensionality, and learning probabilistic dependencies. Moreover, it demonstrates how conditional proba-

bility outputs and scenario tests can inform the design of conservation policies and interventions. The case study in Bristol provides a replicable example for other researchers working with complex social-environmental systems.

Ultimately, the findings underscore that sustainable water and energy use is shaped not by single variables but by embedded routines, enabling infrastructures, and underlying motivations. Effective interventions must therefore adopt a holistic, integrated strategy—aligning behavioural nudges with material improvements and psychological engagement. As computational tools evolve and household-level data become more accessible, Bayesian networks offer a promising path toward more evidence-based, context-sensitive solutions for reducing domestic resource consumption. For practitioners and scholars alike, this framework bridges methodological rigour with real-world impact.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

Chad Staddon is Deputy Editor-in-Chief for this journal and was not involved in the editorial review or the decision to publish this article.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

Supplementary material 1

Summary description of Bayesian network software packages

Authors: Fiorella La Matta Romero

Data type: table, docx

Explanation note: Bayesian Network Software: key features and considerations.

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